

Cover

Verifying and Validating Quantitative Systems Pharmacology and *In Silico* Models in Drug Development: Current Needs, Gaps, and Challenges

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<p>ABSTRACT</p>	<p>The added value of <i>in silico</i> models (including quantitative systems pharmacology models) for drug development is now unanimously recognized. It is, therefore, important that the standards used are commonly acknowledged by all the parties involved. On April 25 and 26, 2019, a multistakeholder workshop on the validation challenges for <i>in silico</i> models in drug development was organized in Belgium. As an outcome, a White Paper is foreseen in 2020 on standards for <i>in silico</i> model verification and validation.</p>